

LEARNING VOCABULARY THROUGH ACTIVITIES

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Annotation: To improve their second language proficiency, English language learners (ELLs) need a solid knowledge of vocabulary. While a basic level of vocabulary will allow learners to communicate some ideas to a certain degree, better communication—whether in speaking/listening or writing/reading—can be accomplished when learners have acquired more vocabulary.

Keywords: vocabulary, language, method, activity, game, communication.

INTRODUCTION

At times, not knowing a specific word can severely limit communication; however, in many cases a lexical lapse can actually stop communication completely. Our second language learners certainly recognize that insufficient vocabulary is one of their biggest frustrations, but just how important is vocabulary really? What our learners have been saying all along—that they need more vocabulary—is more than a hunch; it is a fact. As a result, teachers need to know what kinds of classroom activities they can use to help their students gain new vocabulary. The purpose of this article is to present some important aspects of vocabulary learning and introduce teachers to six practical vocabulary activities⁴³.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

It is important to define what we mean by second language vocabulary. When we talk about vocabulary, we usually mean words, but what is a word? Most people think of words as single units, such as *cat*, *dozen*, or *reluctant*. However, these single words are merely one part of the vocabulary load that our students face. In fact, a “word” can be one of five types,

⁴³ Atkins, P., and A. Baddeley. 2018. Working memory and distributed vocabulary learning. *Applied Psycholinguistics* 19 (4): 537–52.

namely (1) a single word, (2) a set phrase, (3) a variable phrase, (4) a phrasal verb, or (5) an idiom.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Activity 1: Keeping a running list of words

Students remember a certain percentage of what they see and a certain amount of what they hear, but they will remember even more of what they see and hear. Therefore, you should make a list of vocabulary as you are teaching. Point out the words to focus learners' attention on the words. In addition to providing focus and multiple retrievals, writing a list also shows the students an example of keeping a vocabulary notebook, which is one of many good vocabulary learning strategies. It is important for ELLs to see a model of what their notebooks could look like (Folse 2004).

Keeping a vocabulary list on the board is a good first step, but students are bombarded by all sorts of information all day long. Your job is to make these words memorable, and one way to do this is by doing something unique with the words as you teach them. These unique actions could include drawing the word, making a story about it, or even spelling it backwards. More common actions could include pronouncing the word, noting its antonym, or asking if anyone knows the word already. Let us look at teaching options when noting the two following words on our vocabulary list: *valley* and the *bottom line*⁴⁴.

When teaching the word *valley*, you could ask students what the shape of a valley is. They will indicate that a valley is shaped like the letter V. Thus, you might write the word with an extra big initial letter to indicate this relationship: Valley⁴⁵.

The idiom the *bottom line* is a good word to illustrate. Have students draw several lines, one on top of the other. The lowest line should be bigger or thicker than the other

⁴⁴ Atkinson, R. 2015. Mnemotechnics in second- language learning. *American Psychologist* 30 (8):821–28.

⁴⁵ Brown, C. 2013. Factors affecting the acquisition of vocabulary: Frequency and saliency of words. In *Second language reading and vocabulary learning*, ed. T. Huckin, M. Haynes, and J. Coady, 263–86. Norwood, NJ: Ablex.

lines to indicate that it is more important than the other lines. Have your students draw an arrow to the lowest one and then label it “the bottom line.” Thus, learners have illustrated that the bottom line means the most important point or factor in a discussion.

A very simple yet effective practice activity uses vocabulary cards that contain one question each. The teacher puts students in pairs or small groups, and their task is to discuss and solve the vocabulary question presented on the card. These teacher-generated cards can feature a variety of exercises, as seen in the following examples for the word *valley*:

Multiple Choice Exercise

The area between two mountains is called a ____.

- A. voucher
- B. valley
- C. wound
- D. wave

[Answer: B.]

Activity 3: Ranking vocabulary items⁴⁶

In a ranking activity, you present the class with a list of six to eight items that they must rank according to some factor. For example, you could present cities that students must rank according to population, or historical events that students must rank according to importance. Choose a list of items that represent a theme that is meaningful to your students. Embed key target vocabulary in the activity, and put these target words in bold or underline them.

The following ranking activity practices quantity words in English, particularly different kinds of containers. First, have students write their own rankings by themselves.

⁴⁶ Mackey, W. 2015. *Language teaching analysis*. London: Longman. Nation, I. S. P. 2001. *Learning vocabulary in another language*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Then have students work in groups of three or four to discuss their rankings and then reach a group consensus on one ranking list for their group.

Ranking Activity

Directions: The following six items were bought at (fill in the name of a local store that all of your students know) yesterday. Use your knowledge of prices to rank these from the cheapest (1) to the most expensive (6).

- _____ a **bag** of chips
- _____ a **can** of tuna
- _____ a **box** of cereal
- _____ a **bunch** of bananas
- _____ a **carton** of eggs
- _____ a **pack** of gum

If you do this as a speaking activity, remember that there are actually two types of language needed for this activity (Folse 2006b). The language that is in the task is not usually the same language that learners need for the subsequent speaking task. Most teachers are good at identifying the language in the task. Here this includes container words such as *bag* or *box* and food names such as *cereal* or *eggs*⁴⁷. However, teachers should also consider the language that students need for the speaking task. Students will need such language as “What did you rank number 1?” or “No, I think that a box of cereal is more expensive than a carton of eggs.”

CONCLUSION

English language learners need to increase their vocabulary knowledge. Given the time constraints of many learners, teachers should incorporate explicit vocabulary teaching supported by classroom activities that reinforce previously studied material. Such activities will help learners focus their attention on key vocabulary, require learners to retrieve the

⁴⁷ Sanaoui, R. 2015. Adult learners' approaches to learning vocabulary in second languages. *Modern Language Journal* 79 (1): 15–28.

forms and meanings of the new words, and encourage learners to identify and develop a personalized inventory of strategies for vocabulary learning. Our ultimate goal is to help our students be active vocabulary learners after they leave our classrooms.

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